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FUSING TRADITION WITH INNOVATION: BRIDGING ACHIEVEMENT GAPS IN BIOLOGY CLASSROOMS THROUGH BLENDED LEARNING STRATEGIES

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of the use of blended learning strategy on students' achievement in biology at the Senior Secondary School level. Two schools were purposively selected within the area of study. The research design was a quasi-experimental design using the pre-test, post-test non-equivalent group design. The instrument used to gather data was the Variation and Evolution Achievement Test (VEAT) which had a reliability coefficient of 0.73. A total of 75 SS2 biology students comprising 45 females and 30 males participated in the study. The experimental group was taught with the blended learning strategy while the control group was taught with the traditional lecture method. The data (pre-test and post-test scores) collected was analysed using ANCOVA since the participants were not randomly assigned to the groups. The study found a statistically significant difference between the performance of students taught using blended learning and those taught with the traditional lecture method [$F(1,71) = 137.19; p < .05$]. Hence, the study concluded that blended learning is a potent strategy for improving students' performance in biology and promoting meaningful learning. Based on the findings of this study, we recommended that the government and school proprietors should strive to provide the basic technological facilities such as computers, projectors, projector screens, and internet facilities that will be needed by the teachers to deliver effectively.

Keywords:

Blended Learning Strategy, Biology, Achievement

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Introduction

With technological advancements and the expansion of online educational resources, educational institutions worldwide are increasingly incorporating technology into their teaching and learning approaches. Previous research has shown that technology has improved student achievement, classroom engagement, and support for students with special needs (Zucker, 2008). Learning environments incorporated with information technology have specific advantages for learning science in promoting cognitive development, allowing for a broader range of student experiences, promoting students' self-management ability, and supporting students' conceptual understanding by facilitating data collection and collaboration (Webb, 2008).

The creation of innovative and collaborative learning environments has helped ensure that learning is made simple, flexible and effective. Blended learning is one of the emerging innovative and collaborative learning environments that students have shown to be welcoming (Yilmaz & Malone, 2020). Blended learning is a relatively new teaching strategy that, in most educational institutions, has primarily replaced e-learning. It's a fusion between traditional face-to-face and online learning where students are taught in and out of the classroom, with the online component serving as a natural extension of traditional classroom learning (Kazu & Demirkol, 2014). Combining the two learning experiences maximises the positive effects of both learning conditions to achieve the intended learning objectives. Blended learning involves at least three elements: teachers as a mentor, online learning materials, and acquired skills through classroom learning experiences (Yapici & Akbayin, 2012; Adam et al. 2022).

Blended learning allows learners to visualize, listen, and interact with the learning material. In a blended learning classroom, fast learners expand their knowledge and learn things that are not within the school syllabus but vital to the learning process. Meanwhile, slow learners repeat and revise notes and get feedback from their teachers to overcome problems and challenges (Bailey & Martin, 2013). There are seven distinct models of blended learning: face-to-face driver model, rotation model, flex model, labs model, self-blend model, and online driver model.

The knowledge and practice of Biology is as old as humans. As a science subject, biology has made significant contributions to improving our quality of life over the years. The study of biology contributes to increased food and beverage production, preservation, and storage to eradicate malnutrition; production of medicinal drugs to enable people to live a good and healthy life. Biology is vital in the transportation sector because many of the fuels used today have a biological origin. Fossil fuels like natural gas and petroleum are derived from decomposed plant and animal matter. Biology is a compulsory subject for science students in Nigeria and most African countries, and it has tentacles in other science subjects such as physics and chemistry (Federal Republic of Nigeria 2014). This is why some science educators regard biology as the mother of all sciences. Therefore, students' success in biology is equivalent to their success in science.

From the foregoing, biology is undeniably a unique and vital subject whose knowledge is genuinely dear to humans. Despite the importance of biology to humans and national growth and development, students still find some concepts difficult to understand, to learn and to remember, which ultimately leads to their persistent underperformance in both internal and external examinations (Akinbadewa, 2020; Akintoye et al. 2023). Consequently, this underperformance has attracted the attention of several science educators and researchers across the country (Akintola & Odewumi, 2021; Adam et al., 2022). A series of interventions had since been trialed in different parts of the country with a singular aim of improving the performance of secondary school students in biology. Adebajo (2020) believed that whatever difficulty and

misconception students experience in understanding biological concepts is because of how those concepts are taught in the classroom. In essence, Hikmawati and Suryaningsih (2020) proposed the use of blended learning strategy as a solution to the pending problem of teaching biology because it creates an enabling environment in which students learn with freedom and greater flexibility, explores online learning resources, develops students' self-confidence, provides appropriate feedback, and allows students to control time, place, and pace of learning.

In a review of empirical studies, blended learning seems to be more effective than other forms of teaching and learning due to its ability to combine the advantages of both face-to-face interactions and web-based teaching and learning. Yustina, Syafii, & Vebrianto (2020) investigated the impact of blended learning strategy on the creative thinking ability of Biology students. The study revealed that the overall average score of creative thinking ability of students in the blended learning group was higher) compared to in the control class. Li *et al.* (2019), through a systematic review of learning in nursing, found that blended learning approaches can effectively improve knowledge and satisfaction of nursing students but highlight that there is a lack of research on the topic. can effectively improve knowledge and satisfaction of nursing students but highlight that there is a lack of research on the topic. Furthermore, Ilorah, Adeniji & Odeyemi (2018) undertook a study to improve secondary school students' performance in physics practicals using a blended learning strategy. Findings from the study revealed a significant difference in the achievement of students who were taught Physics practical using a blended learning strategy and those taught using the conventional method in favour of the blended learning group. Similarly, Sharma & Sharma (2020) examined the effect of a blended learning strategy on students' achievement in English. Findings from the study revealed that the blended learning group achievement was significantly higher than that of the conventional teaching method in English.

From the foregoing, it was observed that there was hardly any study found on the effect of blended learning strategy on Nigerian secondary school students' achievement in biology. Most of the literature on blended learning is focused on higher education and other secondary school subjects. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of a blended learning strategy on secondary school students' achievement in biology, with a focus on variation and evolution. The choice of variation and evolution was because the West African Examinations Council (WAEC 2019,2020,2021). Chief Examiners' report stressed that candidates showed a poor understanding of variation and evolution. The reports also revealed that many candidates did not attempt questions raised on variation and mutation concepts, while those who attempted the questions performed poorly. Furthermore, a study conducted by Okebukola et al. (2020) ranked concepts in the new biology curriculum for secondary schools in Nigeria and Ghana in order of difficulty from the most perceived difficult concept to the least. The study surveyed 1,499 participants from both countries since they use the same biology syllabus for senior school certificate examinations. Table 1 showed that variation and evolution were the most difficult concepts for students to learn as they ranked 1st of the 20 concepts included in the study.

Hypothesis

1. There will be no statistically significant difference in the academic performance of students taught using blended learning strategy and those taught using the lecture method.

Methodology

The study employed a pretest, post-test and control group quasi-experimental design. The population for the study comprises all biology students in senior secondary schools in Education district V in Lagos State, Nigeria. With over 150 public and private senior secondary schools, educational district V is the largest in the state. Two public schools located in different education zones with relatively similar characteristics regarding teacher's (biology) qualification, school facilities, students' population were randomly selected for the study. It would have been a weakness for the study if the participating schools differed substantially from one another. A total of 75 students in year two at senior secondary school (SS2) participated in the study. The control group made up about 47% of the total participants, while the experimental group accounted for 53%. Students in the SS2 were the preferred choice for the study on the basis that they already have spent one school session (1st term to 3rd term) learning the content, process and ethics of science and they have not been taught the topic (variation and evolution) at the time the study was conducted (1st term of SS2; a new session) based on the structure of the national curriculum. The Variation and Evolution Achievement Test (VEAT) was employed to gather the quantitative data for the study. The instrument had two sections; section A focused on the participants' demographic data, while section B contained 20 discrete items (multiple choice questions) with four options lettered A-D. Each item had three distractors and one key. Content validity of the instruments was ensured by test experts and biology teachers and science educators. The instrument had a reliability coefficient 0.73 which falls within the acceptable range of 0.70 to 0.80 against which most instruments used in educational research are benchmarked (Mohajan 2017).

Data Collection

After obtaining permission from school authorities (principals of schools) to conduct the study, the research team created a welcoming environment in which the respondents felt at ease and ready to participate (this was achieved with the help of the school biology teacher). A pretest was administered to both groups to determine the initial performance of the students. The experimental group received lessons using a blended learning strategy, while the control group was taught with the conventional lecture method. The treatment lasted for three weeks. While the biology teacher of the control group school was retained for the study, the teacher for the experimental class was tutored on how to use a blended learning strategy to deliver instruction effectively. Two sessions of micro-teaching exercises were conducted to ensure mastery of the approach by the teacher. At the end of the week three lesson, the post-test was conducted. The test administration was carefully done with no observable difference in the process for the two groups particularly concerning time allotted and students' willingness to take the test. The two data sets (pretest and posttest scores) generated during data collection for the study were analysed using IBM SPSS version 23 software. Data were analysed using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) at the 0.05 confidence level, with the pre-test scores serving as the covariate to draw the two groups to the same baseline because randomization was not achieved.

Data analysis and findings

Preliminary tests showed that the data satisfied the assumptions of homogeneity of variances ($F = .037$; $P > .05$) and the Shapiro-Wilk's test of normality was favourable for both groups; control group ($N=35$) = .48; $p > .05$ as well as for experimental group: ($N=40$) = .56; $p > .05$. The

one-way ANCOVA statistic applied on the pre-test and post-test scores of the two groups using the pretest scores as the covariate.

Table 1 Mean and standard deviation of post-test scores of the blended learning and lecture method group

Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Blended Learning Group	11.45	2.98	40
Lecture method group	8.25	2.84	35
Total	9.96	3.31	75

The result in Table 6 shows that the blended learning group have a mean value of 11.45 which is higher than that of the lecture method group whose mean value is 8.25. To ascertain whether this observed comparable difference is significant, this result was subjected to inferential testing as shown in table 2 below.

Table 2 Ancova summary table of difference in the achievement of blended learning group and lecture method group.

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Post test scores						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Corrected Model	1542.69 ^a	2	762.33	89.41	.000	
Intercept	1285.47	1	1285.47	150.76	.000	
Pre-test	341.16	1	341.16	40.01	.000	
Method	1169.73	1	1169.73	137.19	0.00	
Error	375.12	71	8.53			
Total	37968.00	74				
Corrected Total	1899.83	75				

a. R Squared = .236 (Adjusted R Squared = .215)

The result in Table 3 shows that at entry level the blended learning group and lecture method group are not significantly different from one another in terms of performance (pretest scores = $p > .05$). However, after been taught, the result shows that the blended learning group and lecture method group differ significantly. [$F(1,71) = 137.19; p < .05$]. Based on this result, the hypothesis which states that there is no statistically significant difference in the achievement of students taught using the blended learning strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture method is therefore rejected.

Discussion

The primary aim of the study was to ascertain whether there existed a statistically significant difference in the academic performance of students instructed through the blended learning approach compared to those taught via traditional lecture methods. It was revealed that students exposed to blended learning exhibited superior academic outcomes in contrast to their counterparts instructed using conventional lecture methods. The capability of students to access

educational resources from diverse locations devoid of spatial limitations, coupled with the facilitation of information exchange and idea dissemination in virtual environments, emerged as contributory factors to their enhanced academic achievements. This finding resonates with the outcomes of preceding studies conducted by Grønlien et al. (2021), which demonstrated that nursing students instructed through blended learning surpassed their peers in face-to-face instructional settings. Additionally, this corroborates the assertions made by Sharma and Sharma (2020), Yilmaz and Malone (2020), and Ceylan and Kesici (2017), who provided empirical evidence supporting the efficacy of blended learning strategies in fostering meaningful comprehension of challenging concepts. However, the findings of the present study are at variance with those reported by Akkoyunlu and Soylu (2008) and Delialioğlu and Yıldırım (2018), indicating the absence of significant discrepancies in student achievement levels based on their learning preferences. Such disparities in findings may be attributed to variations in sample sizes, classroom dynamics, and geographical locations utilized in the respective studies. Moreover, the online component of blended learning facilitates visualisation, thereby enhancing retention (Mayer, 2005; Akinola, 2014). Furthermore, it affords students the opportunity to engage in self-directed learning beyond the confines of traditional classroom settings until they attain proficiency and fulfil their learning objectives. This flexibility allows students to address areas of confusion or misconception that may not be adequately addressed within the constraints of limited classroom interactions. Notably, blended learning accommodates diverse learning styles and aptitudes, particularly catering to students who may require additional time to grasp concepts compared to their peers. It can be inferred that visual learners stand to gain from the visual stimuli presented via computer monitors. Aural learners, on the other hand, will find value in accessing pre-recorded and embedded explanations, instructions, and guides that cater to their auditory preferences. Kinaesthetic learners are likely to benefit from actively engaging in interactive and hands-on activities within the learning environment. Finally, read and write learners may find advantage in the opportunity to take comprehensive notes and reference textual materials available within the blended learning framework, aligning with their preferred mode of learning.

Conclusion and recommendation

The primary objective of this study was to assess whether the implementation of a blended learning approach in teaching biology concepts could result in an improvement in the academic performance of secondary school students. The analysis utilising the ANCOVA test indicated that there existed a statistically significant difference in the academic achievement of students in favor of the group taught with blended learning instruction. Drawing from the findings of this study and acknowledging its limitations, it can be inferred that the adoption of a blended learning strategy has the potential to improve students' academic achievement in biology. This assertion finds support in corroborative research conducted both domestically and internationally. While it is imperative to acknowledge the study's constraints regarding sample size and the scope of biology concepts covered, certain recommendations can still be made:

- It is advisable for biology educators at the senior school level to engage in continuous personal and professional development initiatives, particularly those centred on leveraging new technologies to enhance instructional methodologies. Educators need to appreciate that contemporary classrooms are populated by digital natives who possess inherent familiarity with computer technology and the internet.

- There is a pressing need to revise the curriculum for pre-service teachers, ensuring alignment with the evolving learning preferences and technological adeptness of future generations of students, who are increasingly reliant on technology in their daily lives.
- Governments and educational institutions should prioritise the organisation of comprehensive training and retraining programmes for secondary school biology instructors, focusing on equipping them with the requisite skills to effectively utilise multimedia technologies for content delivery, both within the confines of traditional classroom settings and beyond.

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